

Some Basic Solutions to Improve the Effectiveness of Aesthetic Awareness Education for Students of Hue University

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ABSTRACT: Educating aesthetic awareness for Hue University students in the current period is an extremely urgent requirement, requiring the participation of all levels, sectors and the whole society. There must be fundamental solutions to improve the quality and effectiveness of aesthetic awareness education for students, thereby contributing significantly to the education of personality, ethics and lifestyle for Hue University students in the current period.

KEYWORDS: Aesthetic awareness education, Hue University students

1. Improving the effectiveness of aesthetic education through teaching Aesthetics

Aesthetics is a science that stimulates creativity, to develop the talents that are still cherished in each person. Art is a part of aesthetics. Aesthetics also brings the necessary understanding of the types, genres as well as the achievements of human and national art, thereby improving the ability to perceive and create aesthetics of each person.

Aesthetics also helps people know how to live and create according to the law of beauty; know how to determine for themselves an advanced ideal, know how to distinguish healthy aesthetic tastes from mediocre, backward tastes; thereby building a good life, always following the path of Truth - Goodness - Beauty.

Aesthetics is also the ethics of tomorrow, because when people know how to voluntarily live and act according to the law of beauty, Goodness takes on a new meaning: voluntary, selfless, noble. In the philosophical system of the world's great thinkers, aesthetics is always the conclusion of each person's life of exploration and creation. In that sense, aesthetics is very necessary for other sciences, especially Philosophy, Literature, History, Journalism, Linguistics... and all those who love art, because aesthetics is the methodology of art. Only by understanding aesthetics can one deeply understand art. Therefore, improving the effectiveness of aesthetic awareness education through teaching aesthetics is an extremely urgent requirement in the current period.

2. Innovating the content and methods of aesthetic awareness education for Hue University students in the current period

In terms of the content of aesthetic awareness education for Hue University students, it is necessary to innovate and supplement regularly to suit the reality and development trends of the times. The content of aesthetic awareness education must be further enhanced with respect to the content related to political awareness. Here, within the scope of the study, the author mentions some aspects of political awareness that have a great influence on aesthetic awareness education such as patriotism, national solidarity, the beauty in the consciousness and traditions of the Vietnamese people that have existed for thousands of years so that students are more aware of political issues, making students have "resistance" to the distorted and destructive political ideologies of hostile forces that can corrupt the good aesthetic and moral values of the nation. The content of aesthetic awareness education should aim to preserve and promote cultural values, cultural identity, and good aesthetic values of the nation, and absorb the quintessence of human culture. The content of aesthetic awareness education should guide students to the aesthetic awareness of socialism.

It is necessary to further strengthen the integration of theory and practice into lecturers' lectures, carry out many practical research activities, take students to experience and visit historical sites, famous landscapes, works of art, sculptures, etc. to form vivid visualization for students to develop abstract thinking.

Hue University needs to focus on strengthening the coordination between the activities of the School Youth Union and the activities of socio-political organizations in social activities, volunteering, developing art clubs, attracting a large number of students to participate. Through social activities, volunteering helps students realize the importance of perceiving good moral values of the nation such as patriotism, solidarity, helping each other, etc., thereby improving the trends, abilities and aesthetic awareness of

students, contributing to repelling bad thoughts, tastes and trends, and cultures that are increasingly penetrating a part of today's students.

It is necessary to integrate aesthetic awareness education into subjects for students of Hue University in particular and colleges and universities in Vietnam in general today. Each subject will help students develop in a different aspect of perception and taste as well as stimulate and develop aesthetic capacity for students.

3. Improving the effectiveness of aesthetic education for Hue University students through the movements of the Youth Union and Association

Aesthetic education is an important content in each school in general and Hue University in particular in the current period. To improve the effectiveness of aesthetic education for students, it is necessary to pay more attention to the movements of the Youth Union and Association inside and outside the school. The Youth Union plays an important role in schools, especially in Hue University. Through the activities of the Youth Union and Association movements, students have the opportunity to experience, demonstrate their own abilities and contribute their youth to the development of the country. Youth Union activities play an important role in educating revolutionary ideals, ethics, lifestyles and skills, and aesthetic abilities for union members and young people.

4. Strengthening the coordination between family, school and society in educating aesthetic awareness for students

Family is the cell of society, where each person is born and raised, where the younger generation is cared for physically, mentally and spiritually. Family is also the first educational environment and has a decisive importance in shaping the personality of each individual, therefore, to make the process of educating aesthetic awareness for students most effective, it is necessary to combine it with education from the family.

Aesthetic education in schools is considered the core of educational activities in general and aesthetic education for students at Hue University in particular. It is necessary to pay more attention to aesthetic education for students in schools, so that students have the best conditions to focus on the learning process. Schools need to educate to continuously improve aesthetic taste and art appreciation in students, at the same time helping them identify, prevent and repel all negative, reactionary or destructive manifestations of the spiritual life of society. Educating students about aesthetic awareness is to foster the desire to bring beauty into life, forming in them the ability to perceive, enjoy, evaluate, create and act according to the criteria of beauty.

Authorities at all levels actively propagate the Party's policies and the State's laws, raise awareness and sense of responsibility of everyone, especially young students, in complying with the law, implementing a cultural lifestyle, preventing violations of the law, violations of ethical standards, and violence in society; strengthen management work. Education of aesthetic awareness is one of the important factors in personality education and beauty education for people. Currently, young people in general and students in particular are subject to many objective and subjective impacts that affect the capacity and aesthetic tastes of each student, including negative impacts that deviate from standards in consciousness and practical activities. Therefore, society is an important factor in orienting students about what is true, good, and beautiful.

5. Promoting the positivity and initiative of students in self-awareness of cultivating knowledge in learning and orientation towards beauty, enhancing personal aesthetic awareness

Aesthetic awareness education is a long-term process and requires high self-awareness, for you as students currently studying at Hue University. Carrying the great responsibility of the educational career, more than anyone else, you must be the pioneers in self-education, completing well the tasks of studying and personal awareness to become shining examples for the next generation to follow and learn from.

6. Conclusion

The solutions proposed in this article are meaningful in both theory and practice in educating aesthetic awareness for Hue University students in the current period, helping students gain a perspective, assessment and awareness of beauty and aesthetics, guiding students towards good moral values, contributing to preserving, maintaining and promoting traditional cultural values, absorbing the quintessence of human culture to further cultivate their capacity and aesthetic awareness.

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